

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN RELATION TO ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS IN KALAHANDI DISTRICT OF ODISHA

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Introduction

Odisha is a state of hope in the development dream of the progressing India. Under central government aspirational districts scheme initiative, ten districts from Odisha are chosen. Kalahandi is one of the aspirational districts of Odisha. It has an area of 8,364.89 square kilometers and population around 23 lakhs. It occupies the south western portion of Odisha. The educational status of this district is a measure concern for the government. In the present socio economic and cultural context, the world is becoming more and more competitive. When the quality of performance is regarded as the key factor for personal progress, great emphasis is placed on achievement right from the beginning of the formal institution. This desire for a high level of achievement puts a lot of pressure on students, teachers, schools in particular and the educational system in general. Correlates of achievement are viewed in terms of three domains. These are cognitive, affective and psychomotor. In addition to the innate mental abilities, the non-scholastic factors contribute towards academic achievement. If the student does not cultivate a habit in respect of seriousness in achieving the conquest, he can not show excellence in the field of academics. He must have proper study habit, need for achievement, highest level of aspiration, a good mental health, proper adjustment, interest towards studies etc. for academic excellence. These aspects should be mostly focused in the school environment of aspirational districts.

Mishra (2007) carried out a study on achievement motivation and academic performance of secondary school students. The result showed that boys had more achievement motivation as compared to girls. Socio economic status did not play any role in the achievement motivation of the students. Relationship between achievement motivation

and academic achievement in case of girls was negligible . Bari(2008) In his study on achievement motive and academic achievement of secondary school level in relation to sex found out that there existed significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievements, in case of total sample as well as in case of all sub samples. Awan,Noureen and Naz(2011) Studied the relationship between achievement motivation and achievement in English and mathematics at secondary level . This study examined the achievement and its relationships with achievement motivation . The results revealed that achievement motivation was significantly related to academic achievement . The correlations of all three dimensions of achievement motivation (social, mastery , performance goals)and academic achievement of mathematics are significant at the 0.01 level (two tailed) . The relationship of English and mathematics and three variables of achievement motivation was positive and significant .

Nayak(2013) conducted a study on achievement motivation of higher secondary students as correlates of academic achievement in relation to sex and socio economic status . The study aimed to investigate relationship between achievement motivation with academic achievement The study revealed that there was significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement. Socio economic status played a significant role in the academic achievement of the students .

Mishra(2013) conducted a study on achievement motivation and academic performance of secondary school students in relation to some personal variables . The study was conducted to ascertain the extent to which achievement motivation of secondary school students of different sex and socio economic strata , affected their academic performance .Bhargava's achievement motivation test(1994)was used. Sample consisted of 110 boys and girls in 7 schools of Gangtok city. The study revealed that there was significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic performance . Sex and socio economic status did not influence achievement motivation of the students.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find the relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement of secondary school students.
2. To study the achievement motivation of secondary school students in relation to gender.
3. To study the achievement motivation of secondary school students in relation to type of school.

4.To study the academic achievement of secondary school students in relation to socio economic status variations.

Hypotheses

The following are the hypotheses of the study-

HO1: There is no significant relationship between achievement motivation and academic achievement of secondary school students .

HO2: There is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of secondary school students In relation to gender.

HO3: There is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of secondary school students In relation to type of school management.

HO4: There is no significant difference in the achievement motivation of secondary in relation to Socio-economic status.

Methodology: Descriptive Survey method was used in the present study.

Sample: For the present study a sample of 700 students of secondary level studying in both government and private schools of aspirational districts of Kalahandi were selected with the help of random sampling technique . Out of the 700 students 350 were boys and 350 were girls. Students from both rural and urban areas were taken in the sample .

Tools Used: The following tools were used by the investigators for the collection of data

1. Pratibha Deo and Asha Mohan achievement motivation scale (1985)
2. Socio- economic status scale of Chettri(2015)
3. Academic achievement score of the students were also collected from records.

Major Findings

1. Achievement motivation was found significantly related to academic achievement of the students.
2. Boys of both government and private schools had more achievement motivation as compared to girls.
3. The students of private schools were found to possess more achievement motivation as compared to the students of government schools.
4. Socio economic status was found to play a significant role in the academic achievement of both boys and girls of private and government schools.

Conclusion

The Kalahandi district ranks as aspirational districts on the basis of a composite index comprising of health , education , nutrition , basic infrastructure , poverty etc. Education plays a vital role in the developmental process of this district . Assessment is a complex and essential aspect of teaching and learning process . It is essential to review whether the learning objectives have been achieved ,to what extent the capacities of the learners have been developed and whether desired necessary changes have been brought about In the aptitude , attitude and interest of the learners . The human and natural resources of Kalahandi district can be mobilized if the prime drawbacks in the educational process of different schools of this district can be handled progressively .

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